

INFLUENCE OF LOW-TEMPERATURE CYCLES ON UV/CONDENSATION-SALT SPRAY AGING OF GFRP PULTRUDED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The environmental degradation of pultruded composite gratings used in offshore structures was studied through accelerated artificial aging cycles in climatic chambers, based on ISO 20340 standard. The objective of this work was to evaluate the influence of low-temperature cycles on material aging and its mechanical properties. The specimens were obtained from commercial floor gratings and divided into three groups, which were subjected to no aging, aging cycles with, and aging cycles without the low-temperature step. They were assessed by mechanical and non-destructive testing. The low-temperature cycles had little effect on the surface degradation for the exposure time used.

KEYWORDS

Pultruded; Aging; Low-temperature; Degradation; Grating; Offshore.

INTRODUCTION

Pultruded Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) floor gratings are civil structures used on platforms to reduce maintenance costs due to corrosion and also to promote weight savings. However, these gratings are continuously exposed to environmental agents, being susceptible to physical and chemical degradation.

Environmental agents, such as humidity, ultraviolet (UV) radiation, and temperature, affect individually or synergically, reversibly or permanently, the mechanical performance of composite materials. Changes in physical properties, for example, dimensions, glass transition temperature (T_g), and plasticization may be caused by water absorption, that fills the vacant spaces between polymer chains. UV radiation and humidity contribute also to changes in polymer structure by reactions that break chemical bonds permanently. Furthermore, temperature variations acting simultaneously with other environmental agents induce internal stresses which lead to microcracks nucleation (Barreira-Pinto, 2023).

Therefore, environmental degradation is an important topic to consider when designing structures with composites to ensure long-term performance and safety. Although numerous studies have been developed in this area, some points remain unclear. This is the case of the effect of low-temperature cycles on the environmental degradation of composites, especially in the presence of moisture. For example, Karbhari et al. (2002) concluded that exposing E-glass reinforced vinyl ester composites to low-temperature cycling resulted in damage accumulation and a decrease in their mechanical properties; while Wu et al. (2006), testing E-glass/vinyl ester reinforced skin panels, and Cormier and Joncas (2010) testing a unidirectional E glass-epoxy laminate, showed that there was no significant change in their mechanical properties.

In this context, this work aimed to study the environmental degradation of pultruded composite floor gratings through accelerated artificial aging cycles in climatic chambers, based on ISO 20340 Standard (ISO, 2009a), as well as the influence of freeze-thaw cycles in the microstructure of the material and its

mechanical properties. The specimens were obtained from commercial floor gratings, in the application condition, and divided into three groups. The first group was kept as received, the second one was subjected to aging cycles containing the freezing step, while the third was exposed to the same cycles, but without the freezing step. Both groups were compared using non-destructive (Barcol Hardness and Computed Tomography) and destructive (3-point bending tests) techniques.

Environmental Effects on Composite Materials

Hygrothermal Effect

Since water absorption is conducted into the composite by capillarity and diffusion (Liu et al., 2020), which is in turn a temperature-dependent process, both humidity and temperature effects will be treated together as a hygrothermal effect in this topic. In addition, as the material studied in this work is based on a thermoset polymer matrix, the following explanation will be regarding just thermosets, although thermoplastics are also affected by water absorption.

The polymeric matrix can accommodate solvents of different types, organic or inorganic, inside the vacant spaces between its molecular chains. In this process, the chains are separated from each other, reducing the intermolecular forces (van der Waals forces) responsible for the rigidity of the amorphous phase, as well as increasing the mobility of the chains. As a consequence, the material may have its volume increased, also known as swelling, stretching the chains and decreasing resistance compared to the dry condition, in addition to inducing residual stresses in the case of non-uniform absorption (Barreira-Pinto, 2023).

Water can induce damage to the fibers, matrix, or fiber-matrix interface. When absorbed by the matrix, it causes plasticization, reducing its glass transition temperature (T_g) and rigidity; and hydrolysis, which promotes the scission of polymer bonds, transforming long chains into smaller ones. The former can be reversed when the material is dry, while the latter is irreversible and causes permanent damage to the material. Regarding the fiber-matrix interface, due to its chemical inhomogeneity, it ends up serving as a tunnel for water ingress, mainly in low-quality interfaces, causing a differential swelling, propagation of microcracks, fiber-matrix debonding, and dissolution of the matrix (Liu et al., 2020). The degradation of glass fibers is caused by the extraction of calcium, aluminum, and sodium ions and subsequent replacement by hydrogen ions. The reduction in fiber volume resulting from the loss of material generates high residual stresses, which lead to a reduction of fracture toughness (Karbhari, 2007).

High temperatures increase the aging effects induced by water since they accelerate the diffusion process and affect the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs), especially those with low glass transition temperatures. Due to viscoelasticity, when the ambient temperature is close to/above the T_g , the matrix softens, being unable to provide sufficient stress transfer to the fibers, resulting in stiffness reduction and degradation of the fiber-matrix interface. In this case, the failure is fiber-dominated, showing sudden brittle ruptures of the fiber bundles (Liu et al., 2020).

UV Radiation Effect

The aging generated by UV radiation in polymeric materials, also known as photo-aging, originates from radiation emitted by the sun or artificial light. Because it is highly energetic, it causes a reduction in mechanical properties through the processes of photolysis, photo-catalysis, and/or photo-oxidation in the presence of oxidizing media such as air. However, the radiation must first be absorbed by the matrix to degrade the composite. Therefore, materials that are impervious or protected with UV-resistant coatings are not affected (Barreira-Pinto, 2023).

The degradation promoted by photolysis occurs through the scission of polymeric chains or the generation of cross-links. In the first case, the long chains are broken into small molecules that increase mobility and, in turn, decrease the T_g . The smaller size also facilitates crystallization, making the matrix more brittle. In the case of the formation of cross-links, the process is directly associated with the embrittlement of the matrix and the consequent nucleation of microcracks (Barreira-Pinto, 2023). Other consequences of UV aging are loss of surface gloss, surface discoloration, scratches, resin surface

peeling, formation of cavities by oxidation, marked loss of resin from the outer surface, fibers visible and detached from the surface, and delamination of the surface layer (Karbhari, 2007).

As the region most prone to the effect of UV radiation is up to a depth of 10 μm from the surface, a negligible change in the mechanical properties of the composite is observed (Liu et al., 2020). However, the most significant effects of UV radiation on polymeric composites are not due to the direct action of radiation, which acts superficially, but to the increased susceptibility to moisture absorption through the damaged regions of the composite surface (Karbhari, 2007).

Freeze-Thaw Effect

The effect of exposing composite materials to freeze-thaw cycles in the presence of water/moisture remains unclear. Researchers as Karbhari et al. (2002), Haramis et al. (2000), and Gomez and Castro (1996), concluded that the exposition to low-temperature cycles led to a damage accumulation and a reduction of mechanical properties, while Wu et al. (2006), Comier and Joncas (2010), and Aniskevich et al. (2012) came to an opposite result, showing a negligible change on the assessed mechanical properties.

In (Karbhari et al., 2002), flat and cylindrical specimens of E-glass reinforced vinyl ester composites were subjected to five exposure conditions: (a) room temperature and 50% relative humidity (RH); (b) constant temperature of -10°C ; (c) freeze-thaw cycling at 20% RH; (d) freeze-thaw cycling (between -10°C and 22.5°C) with immersion in deionized water at 22.5°C ; and (e) freeze-thaw cycling with immersion in a 5% NaCl solution (artificial saltwater) at 22.5°C . The thermomechanical properties were assessed by Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), and mechanical properties were obtained through tensile and compression tests. The results showed that the exposure to condition (b) produced a stiffening effect in the matrix and hence minor increases in flat coupon tensile strength and stiffness. However, the freeze-thaw cycling caused an accumulation of damage with a more pronounced effect in aqueous solutions ((d) and (e)). It was assigned to the moisture absorption and consequent hydrolysis of ester groups, as well as fiber-matrix debonding. The glass transition temperature also decreased and changes in viscoelastic transition were seen as a result of freeze-thaw exposure.

In (Wu et al., 2006), it was argued that, in some studies of the freeze-thaw aging effect of composites including (Karbhari et al., 2002), not enough performance indexes were obtained from strength testing to evaluate the degradation of the material. Furthermore, a large amount of data scatter made it difficult to conclude whether or not the material had deteriorated. Taking this into account, a test program was proposed with E-glass/vinyl ester coupons subjected to a constant freezing condition (-17.8°C) and a freeze-thaw cycling condition (between 4.4 and -17.8°C), both immersed in distilled or salt water under a strain of 25% of the ultimate strain. Destructive flexural and non-destructive vibration modal tests measured the possible deterioration of the specimens in different numbers of freeze-thaw cycles. The results revealed that freeze-thaw cycling alone caused an insignificant or no change in flexural strength, storage modulus, and loss factor for specimens conditioned in dry air, distilled water, and saltwater. The flexural strength was considered statistically insignificant considering the data scatter.

Therefore, given the aforementioned results, this work aimed to study and better understand the influence of low-temperature cycles, i.e., freeze-thaw cycles, on the aging process of GFRP pultruded composites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material and sampling

This study used a commercial grating of a glass fiber-reinforced phenolic matrix composite, commonly employed on the floor of oceanic structures. The grating consists of several parallel "I" profiles, connected transversally by circular bars, both produced by pultrusion, as schematically shown in Figure 1a. The pultruded profiles have a continuous glass fiber core, a superficial layer of Mat, and a coating with UV protection paint (see Figure 1b). The top of the grating has a non-slip surface, with quartz particles (Figure 1c). The dimensions of each panel are 1m wide and 6m long.

Figure 1: a) Schematic representation of the grating; b) Pultruded profile structure (adapted from (Lichtgitter GmbH, 2020)); and c) Non-slip surface.

To obtain the samples, the grating panel (6.0m x 1.0m) was cut using a Cortag Zapp 200 G2 electric cutter with a circular diamond saw with water cooling. The specimens were defined to have 3 “I” profiles and 3 crossbars, with the central crossbar position being half the length of the test specimen (see Figure 2). The nominal dimensions of the specimens were 39mm thick, 115mm wide, and 470mm long. A total of 12 specimens were obtained and randomly distributed in 5 groups of 3 samples each: 1 group of control samples (CTR group), 2 groups of samples to be aged with low-temperature cycles (LOW groups), and 2 groups of samples to be aged without the low cycles (AGD groups).

Figure 2: Specimen photographed in 3 different views with scale.

Aging cycles

The basic aging cycle was based on ISO 20340 Standard (ISO, 2009a) (with modifications) and is presented in Figure 3. Each cycle lasts 168 hours and consists of 3 steps: 72 hours of alternated cycles of 8 hours under UV-B radiation and 4 hours under a condensed water vapor atmosphere; 72 hours of exposition to neutral salt spray (saline mist); and 24 hours of exposition to low temperature: $-20\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Step 1 UV/Condensation												Step 2 Saline Mist	Step 3 Low Temperature
8h	4h	8h	4h	8h	4h	8h	4h	8h	4h	8h	4h	72h	24h

Figure 3: Basic aging cycle.

The UV/Condensation steps were conducted using the QUV Accelerated Weathering Tester, from Q-Lab Corporation, Model Q-FOG/SSP600. This procedure followed the ASTM G154-16 (ASTM International, 2016). The test was performed using UVB-313 lamps at $70\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and condensation at $50\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$, respectively to each cycle. The Saline Mist step used the Q-FOG Cyclic Corrosion tester, from Q-Panel Lab Products, model Q-FOG/CCT600. The test was according to ISO 9227 Standard (ISO, 2009b). The Low-temperature step used the climatic chamber CC 2000UR. The samples of the CTR group were kept as received, the LOW groups were aged using the complete aging cycle, and the AGD groups were aged without the low-temperature cycles. Table 1 shows the sample identification and the number of aging cycles by group.

Table 1: Aging cycles by groups and sample identification.

Group	Aging cycles	Sample identification
Control (CTR)	0	CTR01, CTR02, CTR03
With low temperature (LOW)	2	LOW21, LOW22, LOW23
	4	LOW41, LOW42, LOW43
Without low temperature (AGD)	2	AGD21, AGD22, AGD23
	4	AGD41, AGD42, AGD43

Testing

Hardness test

The hardness tests were performed using the Barcol scale according to the ASTM D2583-13a (ASTM International, 2013) standard. The Barcol hardness tester was an MTK-1020 portable meter. Hardness was measured in three positions (Figure 4), totalizing thirty measurements per specimen: ten on the upper surface, ten on the lower surface, and five on each lateral surface. A minimum distance of 3mm between measurements and to the edge of the sample was employed. Before performing the hardness measurements, the specimen's upper surface was sanded on the measuring points to reduce its high surface roughness attending to the smoothness requirements for the penetration of the needle during the hardness measurements. An auxiliary device was designed to access the lateral of the specimens and to allow their fixation during the hardness measurements (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: Hardness test setup for a) Upper surface; b) Lateral surface; and c) Lower surface.

Computed Tomography (CT)

The CT scan was performed in one specimen per group. The samples to be analyzed were randomly selected to avoid any bias. The specimens were submitted to two micro-CT analyses, one before and one after the aging treatments. A Phoenix-Xray model GE tomograph with a tube voltage of 120kV and a current of $200\mu\text{A}$ was employed for the tests. Two scans were performed to inspect both halves of the volume and cover the entire specimen. Each scan produced 1200 slices.

Flexural test

The specimen dimensions do not agree with all the requirements of the ASTM standards for bending in pultruded structures. For this reason, the recommendations of the ASTM D8069-17a, ASTM D790-19, and ASTM D7745-19 standards (ASTM International, 2017b, 2017a, 2019) were followed whenever they were suitable for the geometric conditions of the specimen. The specimens were tested using a three-point flexural (3-point bending) device with a load application point (loading nose) centered between the supports (see Figure 5). A 2mm thick rubber was interposed between the loading nose and the specimen to improve the contact between the roller and the surfaces of the specimen and improve the load distribution between the profiles. The test conditions are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Flexural test conditions.

Span	Speed of testing	Support rollers	Loading nose	Failure criteria	Temperature	Testing machine
269mm	6.35 mm/min	Ø25mm 60HRC	Ø25mm 60HRC	13mm displacement	Room temperature	Servo-hydraulic Instron, model 1312, equipped with 50 kN load cell

Figure 5: Flexural test setup.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For this section, when mentioning the aging groups, e.g., “LOW2”, read the average of the measurements (hardness or maximum flexural load) for the three samples of this group (LOW21, LOW22, and LOW23).

Hardness testing

The intrinsic heterogeneity of the composite material, combined with the difference in hardness between the glass fiber and the polymeric matrix, can increase the scatter of the results. All surfaces were evaluated (upper, lower, and lateral) to account for the effects of material heterogeneity using analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a significance level (α) of 0.05.

According to the ANOVA of the results presented in Table 3, the upper surface showed a significant reduction in its hardness values after 4 aging cycles, when exposed to low-temperature (LOW4 group). A p-value of 0.011 was found when comparing CTR, AG4, and LOW4. The Tukey test, a multiple comparison procedure, indicated p-values of 0.025 and 0.013 for LOW4-AGD4 and LOW4-CTR comparisons, respectively, which means that only the LOW4 group showed a significant difference.

The same analysis was done to evaluate the lower surface, which showed a significant difference for the AGD2 and LOW2 groups (ANOVA p-value of 0.031) when comparing CTR, AG2, and LOW2, although AGD2-LOW2 comparison did not reject the null hypothesis (Tukey p-value of 0.627). After 4 aging cycles, both AGD4 and LOW4 presented a significant difference in hardness compared with CTR (Tukey p-values of 0.011 and 0.001, respectively), while AGD4-LOW4 comparison still did not reject the null hypothesis (Tukey p-value of 0.109). No difference in lateral hardness was observed after 2 and 4 aging cycles. All previously discussed results can be confirmed in Figure 6, where trends in hardness values are graphically represented.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation (SD) of the average Barcol Hardness for the CTR, AGD, and LOW groups in each surface (units in HBa).

Surface	CTR		AGD2		AGD4		LOW2		LOW4	
	mean	+/- SD								
Upper	28	3	25	6	29	1	26	1	21	2
Lower	51	3	42	3	41	1	39	5	36	3
Lateral	38	5	32	3	30	3	30	1	32	2

Figure 6: Comparison of average Barcol Hardness between samples of CTR, AGD, and LOW groups for a) 2 aging cycles and b) 4 aging cycles in each surface (error bars represented by +/- one SD).

Indeed, according to the Barcol Hardness test results, the low-temperature cycles increase the surface degradation on the upper surface, as observed after 4 aging cycles (LOW4). Since the upper surface has been modified to suit smoothness requirements, a thorough assessment must be performed to evaluate the effects of surface treatment on hardness results. No significant effects were found on the lower and lateral surfaces, although a decreasing trend is seen in Figure 6b for the lower surface. In this case, the high standard deviation is probably responsible for omitting the difference between AGD4 and LOW4.

Computed Tomography (CT)

After the CT reconstruction, it was possible to generate 2D projections in three perpendicular axes (Figure 7a). Internal discontinuities were identified in all I-beam profiles. These discontinuities were constant throughout the entire profile (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: 3D reconstruction of CT scans with a) Planes in 3 perpendicular axes; b) I-beam cross-section; and c) Specimen length cross-section (discontinuities indicated by arrows).

The comparison between the initial and aged state (Figure 8) for the same specimen did not present any sign of changes, even considering the longer aging (4 cycles) treatment. The proposed aging cycles were not effective to show a significant damaging effect on internal discontinuities, which means that the water absorption could not have reached and affected them. Thus, it was not possible to evaluate the influence of low-temperature cycles on aging using the computed tomography technique.

Figure 8: Computed tomography results for LOW41 specimen of a) initial state before aging; b) aged state after 4 cycles; and c) section plane.

Flexural test

All the results of the flexural test were gathered in Table 4. They were submitted to two analyses of variance, comparing CTR, AGD2, and LOW2 between themselves, as well as CTR, AGD4, and LOW4. In the first analysis, the null hypothesis was not rejected (p-value of 0.997), which means that the average maximum flexural load did not have a significant difference between CTR, AGD2, and LOW2 for a significance level (α) of 0.05. The same statements can be made for the second analysis (CTR, AGD4, and LOW4), which presented a p-value equal to 0.146. Figure 9 graphically shows what was said earlier. The common failure modes visually detected were localized compression (under roller) and shear failures on the lateral surface (Figure 10).

Table 4: Results of flexural test represented by maximum loads in kN.

Sample number	CTR0	AGD2	AGD4	LOW2	LOW4
1	21.8	20.9	21.8	19.5	21.1
2	18.6	19.9	22.2	19.4	21.1
3	19.9	19.3	21.7	21.4	21.8
Mean	20.1	20.0	21.9	20.1	21.3
Standard Deviation (SD)	1.6	0.8	0.3	1.1	0.4

Figure 9: Comparison of average maximum loads between samples of CTR, AGD, and LOW groups for a) 2 aging cycles and b) 4 aging cycles (error bars represented by +/- one SD).

Figure 10: Failure modes observed during flexural test represented by a) localized compression failure and b) shear failure (indicated by arrows).

CONCLUSION

According to the results obtained in the Barcol Hardness test, it was possible to verify a significant degradation effect of low-temperature cycles on the upper surface of the material. Statistically, only the upper surface indicated a significant reduction in hardness after 4 cycles. As it is a surface modified by sanding, a more detailed evaluation of this region is necessary. Despite decreasing trends in lower surface hardness, it was not possible to detect a significant difference between cycles with and without low temperatures. This result could be explained by the higher standard deviation presented by LOW4.

In the case of computed tomography, the projections on the 3 perpendicular axes before and after 4 aging cycles did not indicate any evidence of changes in the shape of the discontinuities. Probably, the number of cycles was insufficient to allow UV radiation and water absorption to affect the grating.

Finally, the average maximum bending load results did not indicate any change that was significant between the groups with and without exposure to low-temperature cycles. The number of aging cycles used was not sufficient to observe significant effects of the low-temperature cycle, except for the HBa measurements on the upper surface. Other non-destructive techniques should be evaluated as alternative methods to the hardness test, especially those that are less sensitive to the heterogeneity of the composite and present less dispersion in the results.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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